

Experimental investigations on load redistribution in composite beams with web openings

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ABSTRACT

In multi-storey and industrial construction, steel-concrete composite floor systems with a high degree of installation are increasingly being used. Technical equipment is guided through web openings in steel beams to reduce overall building height. However, openings in the beam web create local disruptions leading to load redistributions, which need to be considered in the design of steel and concrete parts and the composite connectors. The current European design standard for steel-concrete composite structures does not address web openings in composite beams. In Germany, design rules for plain steel beams with web openings are provided in DAST Guideline 015. However, this guideline does not account for the shear capacity of the concrete slab or the redistributions between the steel web and concrete chord, which significantly affect the overall load-bearing capacity of composite beams in and around a web opening.

The redistribution of shear forces results in additional tensile forces in the shear connectors at one opening edge. In a series of ten pull-out tests with headed studs, the activation of shear connectors at this opening edge is investigated. Varied parameters in the test series include the number and diameter of headed studs, the height of the remaining web in the opening, an optional reinforcement of the remaining web, and the use of a profiled sheet as a composite floor. This approach allows for the assessment of the influence of stiffness ratios on the load transfer and the number of shear connectors involved in load transfer.

Keywords: steel-concrete composite construction, composite beams, web openings, headed studs, pull-out tests

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Composite beams with web openings

In multi-storey and industrial construction, steel-concrete composite floor systems with a high degree of installation are increasingly being utilized. Installation techniques are guided through web openings in steel beams to reduce overall building height. However, these openings in the beam web create local disruptions leading to load redistributions (1, 2). The portion of lateral forces resulting from the absence of the steel beam's web must predominantly be transferred through the concrete chord. This results in additional, locally concentrated stresses in the remaining steel beam and concrete chord, which need to be considered in the design of composite floors or beams. The current version of the Eurocode 4 as the European design standard for steel-concrete composite structures does not address web openings in composite beams (3). In Germany, guidelines for plain steel beams with web openings are provided in DAST Guideline 015 (4). However, these guidelines do not account for the shear capacity of the concrete slab or the redistributions between the steel

web and concrete flange, which significantly affect the overall load-carrying capacity of composite beams in the vicinity of a web opening.

1.2 Background for experimental investigations

In the area of a web opening in a composite beam, shear forces that would otherwise be carried by the steel web must be transferred through the concrete chord. This results in additional tensile forces at the opening's edge oriented towards the load introduction due to redistribution, necessitating the tensile engagement of composite connectors (cf. Fig. 1a and b). A central objective of the presented research is to gain insights into the number of composite connectors involved in load transfer within the disrupted zone and the influences of various geometrical properties. The pull-out tests globally represent the tensile-loaded edge of an opening in a composite beam, enabling a decoupled examination of local load behaviour (cf. Fig. 1b and c).

Fig. 1: a) and b) Local effects of an opening in composite beams and c) derivation of test principle

2 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

2.1 Test specimens and setup

In a series of ten pull-out tests with headed studs, the activation of shear connectors at the tension-loaded opening edge is investigated (five parameter configurations with two tests each). Varied parameters in the test series include the number and diameter of headed studs, the height of the remaining web in the opening, an optional reinforcement of the remaining web, and the use of a profiled sheet as a composite floor (cf. Table 1). This approach allows for the assessment of the influence of stiffness ratios on the load transfer and the number of shear connectors involved in load transfer. The experimental setup and the dimensions of the specimens are depicted in Fig. 2a and b. The location of the headed studs is shown exemplarily for the 2 x 16 mm configuration. This configuration is used as a reference for the investigations. As stated above, the test setup describes the side of an opening under tensile force. The cut-out part of the web represents half of a virtual opening as shown in Fig. 1. The height of the opening is varied by keeping part of the web (“residual web”, Fig. 2a). In two specimens, the residual web is additionally reinforced by two metal sheets. Additionally, the influence of a profiled sheet used as composite floor is investigated in one configuration. The properties and varied parameters of the investigated specimens are described in Table 1. The concrete is reinforced with $5\varnothing 20$ mm in the top layer with no shear reinforcement in the load introduction zone. Additional secondary reinforcement with a diameter of 12 mm was placed in the lower layer and the edges, respectively, and shear reinforcement with a diameter of 8 mm was located at the supports. The cubical compressive strength of the concrete is shown in Table 2.

The specimens are placed on the ground and braced downward via two massive steel trusses. The tensile load is introduced in the remaining web next to the opening via a tension rod connected to the hydraulic cylinder. The load is increased in steps of 50 kN until failure.

Table 1. Test specimens, properties and reached maximum loads

Specimen	Parameter	Headed studs rows x diameter	h_{sc} mm	f_y/f_u MPa/MPa	t_w mm	$t_{w,o}$ mm	$h_{w,o}$ mm	F_{max} kN
LE15B2x16.1	Reference	2 x 16 mm	125	350/450	10	-	-	320
LE15B2x16.2		2 x 16 mm	125	350/450	10	-	-	329
LE15B1x22.1	Dowel geometry	1 x 22 mm	125	350/450	10	-	-	235
LE15B1x22.2		1 x 22 mm	125	350/450	10	-	-	248
LE15B2x16RS.1	Residual web	2 x 16 mm	125	350/450	10	15	60	407
LE15B2x16RS.2		2 x 16 mm	125	350/450	10	15	60	438
LE15B2x16VS.1	Reinforced residual web	2 x 16 mm	125	350/450	10	55	60	539
LE15B2x16VS.2		2 x 16 mm	125	350/450	10	55	60	519
LE15B2x16PB.1	Composite floor	2 x 16 mm	125	350/450	10	-	-	241
LE15B2x16PB.2		2 x 16 mm	125	350/450	10	-	-	248

To measure the deformations of the system various types of measurement equipment were installed (Fig. 2c and d). First, LVDTs were placed at different places on the flange to measure the vertical slip, i.e., uplift. Additionally, LVDTs were installed to measure the horizontal slip between the flange and the concrete. Four headed studs in the middle of the specimen were equipped with strain gauges on two sides, oriented towards the supports, respectively. Next to the conventional measuring equipment, one side of the specimen is monitored via three-dimensional digital image correlation (DIC). By extending the speckle field over the flange and the concrete surface, both the slip and the uplift can be recorded over the entire length. The applied tensile force is recorded via the cylinder. The test setup is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 2: Dimensions of the specimens: a) front view, b) top view and measurement equipment: c) top view, d) front view

Fig. 3: Experimental test setup and used measurement equipment

2.2 Test results

The failure of all test specimens occurred in the form of a concrete break-out (Fig. 4). The ultimate loads F_{\max} achieved by the individual test specimens are shown in Table 1. The test series LE15B2x16 is used as a reference to compare the ultimate loads. Two main trends can be derived from the load capacities achieved. The presence of a residual web and an additional reinforcement both lead to an increase in the maximum load achieved (+30 % and +63 %, respectively). The reason for this is the activation of additional headed studs due to the stiffer opening area. The reduction in the number of dowels with almost the same cross-sectional area (2 x 16 mm to 1 x 22 mm) leads to a significant reduction in the maximum achievable load (-25 %). The single-row arrangement of the dowels results in a narrower concrete break-out cone and therefore also a lower load-bearing capacity. Similarly, the reduction of the concrete chord height in the tested composite floor cross-section leads to a reduction in the load-bearing capacity, as the break-out cone and thus the resistance of the concrete is also reduced (-25 %). The break-out cone varies in size depending on the stiffness of the opening area. It is noticeable that the break-out cone on the side with the regular web is comparable in size for most specimen configurations, whereas the length of the break-out cone increases in the opening for the stiffer configurations.

Fig. 4: Failure by break-out of concrete, L_{bo} shown in a cut-open specimen

The measurement of the vertical slip can be used to analyse which areas of the specimen are activated by the pull-out force. The comparison of the specimens shows the expected behaviour of more headed studs being activated with increasing stiffness of the opening area. In Fig. 5 the uplift measurements of specimen LE15B2x16.1 and LE15B2x16RS.1 are depicted for various loads. The evaluations were made by using LVDTs and DIC. The spatial measurement of the DIC system allows for a measurement of the difference in vertical slip between the flange and the concrete along the length of the specimen. The measurement results are in good accordance with the LVDTs which shows the overall functionality of the system. Two trends can be described from the shown measurements. First, the specimen with residual web in the opening area (LE15B2x16RS.1, cf. Fig. 5f) shows less uplift in general at 300 kN than the reference specimen (LE15B2x16.1, cf.

Fig. 5c). Additionally, the vertical slip increases in the regular web-area, which emphasizes the distribution of the forces. Second, when almost reaching the maximum load capacity, for a stiffer opening area, the uplift increases towards opening area. This could be an indicator for more shear connectors being activated. The measured strains of the headed studs around the opening area show a different behaviour as well. For the reference specimen, the shear connector closest to the opening (connector 3) reaches its yield strain (1.7 ‰) at an early stage (cf. Fig. 5a). This results in a redistribution of the load towards the adjacent studs, mostly towards the opening. The pull-out force of the specimen with a residual web is evenly distributed between the shear connectors and remain lower overall even at higher loads (cf. Fig. 5d). For this specimen, the rows 2 and 3 of the headed studs are activated the most. The horizontal slip between the flange and the concrete confirms these observations. The opening area of the reference specimen can only transfer less horizontal tension forces (cf. Fig. 5b) than the specimen with a residual web (cf. Fig. 5e) due to a smaller tensile stiffness of the flange. As expected, the horizontal slip of specimen LE15B2x16RS.1 is larger which shows the effect of the additional tensile stiffness. These results show the presence of horizontal forces despite the solely vertical loading which have to be considered later.

Fig. 5: Measuring results (strain in headed studs, horizontal slip and vertical slip) for specimens a) – b) LE15B2x16.1 and d) – f) LE15B2x16RS.1

The described behaviour can be applied to the other specimen not shown here (e.g., the additional reinforcement of the opening area). Overall, a stiffer opening area results in more shear connectors being activated and more inclusion of the opening area for load transfer. The results can be summarized as follows:

- *In the case of a concrete failure by breaking out, two rows of headed studs achieve a higher failure load compared to only one row of headed studs, even if the cross-section surface almost stays the same.*
- *The use of a profile sheet as a composite floor decreases the failure load by subtracting contributing concrete.*
- *The stiffer the opening area, the more the load is distributed between the shear connectors and the higher is the achievable failure load.*
- *A stiffer opening area results in more shear connectors being activated in the opening area.*

2.3 Activation of shear connectors

The uniform failure pattern of the test specimens allows for an appropriate comparability. Based on the initial test results, conclusions are drawn about the number of activated shear connectors in the opening area. For this purpose, the break-out cone created during failure is analysed first whose size provides information about the number of activated shear connectors. The exemplarily shown break-out cone (cf. Fig. 4) describes the condition at the end of the test, after the maximum load capacity is surpassed. The breaking out of some dowel rows could be a secondary failure because of the large deformations. For this reason, the point of failure is analysed in more detail by using the DIC images. In Fig. 6 the vertical deformation measured via DIC is depicted for various load-levels (specimen LE15B2x16.1). Fig. 6a and b show the specimen before reaching the maximum load, Fig. 6c the exact moment when reaching maximum load, and Fig. 6d the specimen after failure. The failure occurs quite abrupt. Only when reaching the maximum load, the break-out cone announces itself in the middle of the specimen, where the load is introduced. The shape of the cone quickly develops the horizontal way after surpassing the maximum load.

Fig. 6: Vertical deformation measured via DIC at different load-levels and visualisation of initial break-out cone

For fastenings in structural concrete, ELIGEHAUSEN AND MALLÉ (5) described different failure modes for headed studs set in concrete. Accordingly, a headed stud under tension force can fail by steel failure, by pulling-out of the concrete, by splitting the concrete or by breaking-out of the concrete. The breaking-out of the concrete is the failure mode observed in the experiments. For this failure mode a design equation is given which is extended for a whole group of (shear) connectors.

The basic equation for the load capacity of one (shear) connector $N_{u,c}^0$ (consists of various parameters (cf. Eq. (1)). The first calibrating parameter k is dependent on the kind of connector used (drilled in dowel or headed stud set in concrete) (6). The effective height h_{eff} is shown in Fig. 7a. The remaining parameters are the cubical concrete strength β_w and factors for taking into account various influences (in the following order: surface reinforcement, cracked concrete, eccentric load application).

The load capacity of a single shear connector can then be used to calculate the break-out force of whole group of shear connectors (cf. Eq. (2), Fig. 7b) (7). For this, the basic value is multiplied with the ratio of the existing projected area of the break-out cone of the anchor group $A_{c,N}$ and a single anchorage $A_{c,N}^0$.

$$N_{u,c}^0 = k \cdot h_{\text{eff}}^{1,5} \cdot \sqrt{\beta_w} \cdot \psi_{re,N} \cdot \psi_w \cdot \psi_{ec,N} \quad (1)$$

$$N_{u,c} = N_{u,c}^0 \cdot \frac{A_{c,N}}{A_{c,N}^0} = N_{u,c}^0 \cdot \frac{(3 \cdot h_{\text{eff}} + e_q) \cdot L_{bo}}{9 \cdot h_{\text{eff}}^2} \quad (2)$$

By converting the design equation, the length of the break-out cone L_{bo} can be determined from the achieved test load (cf. Fig. 7b). This in turn can be used to determine the number of activated headed studs, i.e., rows of headed studs. The use of the formula represents the first attempt to predict the number of activated shear connectors. To compare the size of the break-out cone with the calculations, the former has been measured on the failed test specimens. The width of the break-out cone, which was assumed to be fix, is in good accordance with the theory, so that the remaining varying parameter is L_{bo} . The measured (index: bo,meas) and calculated (index: bo,calc) length of the break out cone are shown in Table 2 for all test specimens. The measurements are taken after failure on the fully developed break-out cone.

Fig. 7: Break-out cones of a) a single headed-stud and b) a dowel group

Table 2. Comparison of the measured and calculated size of the break-out cone

Specimen	$f_{c,cube}$ MPa	$L_{bo,meas}$ cm	$L_{bo,calc}$ cm	Δ_L -
LE15B2x16.1	41.8	96	96	1.00
LE15B2x16.2	41.8	100	99	0.99
LE15B1x22.1	42.5	88	87	0.99
LE15B1x22.2	42.5	89	91	1.03
LE15B2x16RS.1	48.9	100	113	1.13
LE15B2x16RS.2	48.9	108	122	1.13
LE15B2x16VS.1	42.2	123	161	1.31
LE15B2x16VS.2	42.2	124	155	1.25
LE15B2x16PB.1	41.7	71	72	1.02
LE15B2x16PB.2	41.7	99	75	0.76

2.4 Evaluation and outlook

When using the design approach, a high level of agreement between the calculated and observed break-out cone can be achieved. The agreement is higher for the specimens without residual web in the opening area. The break-out cones of the test specimens with residual or reinforced web are smaller than predicted by the design equation. Secondary effects must be therefore taken into account (e.g., the support of the flange on the concrete surface in the event of uneven loading). Although the load is applied in the middle of the specimen, the response of opening area and the regular area differ strongly due to stiffness. The design equation is only valid for stiff anchor plates, which can transfer the force evenly. This only applies to the area with the regular web. The opening area, i.e. solely the flange, is flexible and cannot transfer the pull-out force to the headed studs located further away from load application. For this reason, the equation has to be split into two components, in a “basic” resistance and an “additional” resistance resulting from the variable stiffness of the opening area. The additional resistance generated by the flange opening area is comparable to an anchor rail due to the lack of stiffness (8). When increasing the stiffness by adding a residual web or a reinforcement, the behaviour becomes more similar to a stiff anchor plate.

When considering various stiffnesses along the length of the dowel group area, the load introduction becomes eccentric in theory. When the force generates the initial uplift, the web would rotate around the last dowel (cf. Fig. 5, dowel 5) but the attached flange of the opening area is subjected to a tensile force which (partly) neutralizes the rotational movement and generates additional tension forces in the flange. Additionally, the location of the introduced force was chosen arbitrary. In this test setup, the load introduction is positioned between the last and penultimate headed stud in front of the opening. In a global system the load introduction would not be that concentrated and potentially located differently. The tension force of the flange equals to a highly eccentric load pulling on an anchor rail. This must be considered in a future design concept.

3 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Ten pull-out tests were carried out to assess the load transfer behaviour of headed studs at the edge of web openings. The specimens depict the side of a web opening which transfers tension forces into the concrete chord. Several parameters were varied, e.g., the stiffness of the opening area and the arrangement of the headed studs. All specimens failed by breaking out of the concrete. The size of the concrete break-out cone increases with higher stiffness of the opening area, which results in a higher break-out force. The reduction from two to one row of headed studs (similar cross-section) resulted in a lower load capacity. The break-out cones created during failure are analysed to determine the number of activated shear connectors. A design equation for fastenings in structural concrete is then used to calculate the break-out force and the number of activated shear connectors. The calculated and measured sizes of break-out cones show good agreement, with some variations

attributed to secondary effects. These effects result from a difference in stiffness of the opening area and the regular web. The future goal is to modify the design equation to account for the different stiffnesses of the opening area and the web, and the varying stiffness of the opening area itself. The described results will be verified by a series of experimental investigation on real size composite beams to be able to consider additional global effects.

The results presented are extracts from the research project IGF (*collaborative industrial research*) No. 21429 N/2 / FOSTA (*Research Association for steel Application*) P1478 "Consistent design model for steel composite beams with web openings". We would like to take this opportunity to thank the German Federation of Industrial Research Associations (AiF) for its support.

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